

Temple at Tel Arad

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**Supervised Entry, prepared from a literature review by a student or students under the direction of a Supervisor, typically as a classroom project; edited and vetted by Supervisor.*

Entry tags: Canaanite Religions, Religious Group, Religious Place, Levantine Religion, Temple

The Temple of Tel Arad is located within the military fort of Arad in the semi-arid Beersheba-Arad valley of the northeastern Negev in the southern Levant. The site of Tel Arad itself was originally excavated by Yohanon Aharoni and Ruth Amiran from 1962-1967. A final report for these excavations was never published, though substantive preliminary reports were published by Herzog (2002) and Singer-Avitz (2002). As a result of early excavation methodology, subsequent building atop the site, and slow progress toward publication, the exact dating of the Temple has been contested. The temple was originally understood as in use from the 10th through the end of the 8th century BCE (Stratum XI-VIII), a period of 350 years (Herzog et al. 1984). However, a re-evaluation of the stratigraphy and material culture have clarified that it was only operational in Stratum X and IX, a period of 50 years spanning from the middle to the late 8th century BCE with its termination appearing to predate the invasion of Judah by the the Assyrian Empire under Sennacherib in 701 BCE (Herzog 2002: 14, 49-50). During the 8th century BCE this region and the fort of Tel Arad were under the sway of the Judahite administration based in Jerusalem. As such, and while we lack specific textual or inscriptional data dating to this period, we may postulate that certain features of Judahite religious practice as indicated within the Hebrew Bible were also present in the Temple at Tel Arad. Thus, it is more than likely that the deity of the focus in the Temple at Arad was Yahweh (and a consort?). The temple measures 12 by 18 m and comprised nearly one sixth of the available space within the fort, demonstrating its importance to those within. The temple presents a tripartite division with an outer courtyard containing a large altar of unhewn stones for animal sacrifices, a main hall (hêkāl) with its interior walls surrounded by stone benches, and an innermost sacred area (dēbîr). Inside this room was a standing stone (maššēbah) on a small platform. Incense altars from the site bear evidence of the burning of frankincense and cannabis (Arie et al. 2020). The Temple at Arad was decommissioned at the end of the 8th century BCE, with its ritual cancellation resulting in the removal of the majority of material culture from within it. The lack of destruction suggests it may not have been the target of a series of religious reforms (2 Kings 18) as was previously assumed (Herzog 2010). Nonetheless, subsequent the cancellation of the temple, the worship of Yahweh became increasingly centralized in Jerusalem.

Date Range: 750 BCE - 705 BCE

Region: Temple at Tel Arad

Region tags: Levant, Israel, Palestine, Negev, Judah

The Temple at Tel Arad, located in the Beersheba-Arad Valley of the northeastern Negev.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." *Tel Aviv* 29 (1): 3-109.
- Source 2: Herzog, Ze'ev. 2010. "Perspectives on Southern Israel's Cult Centralization: Arad and Beer-Sheba." In *One God – One Cult – One Nation: Archaeological and Biblical Perspectives*, edited by R. G. Kratz and H. Spieckermann, 169-99. Berlin & New York: Walter de Gruyter.
- Source 3: Zevit, Ziony. 2001. *The Religions of Ancient Israel: A Synthesis of Parallaxic Approaches*. New York: Continuum.

Notes: For a discussion of the pottery and ostraca from the site see: Signer-Avitz, Lily. 2002. "Arad: The Iron Age Pottery Assemblages." *Tel Aviv* 29 (1): 110-214. Aharoni, Yohanan. 1981. *Arad Inscriptions*. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society. For a discussion of older interpretations of the stratigraphy of Iron Age Arad see: Aharoni, Yohanan. 1968. "Arad: Its Inscriptions and Temple." *The Biblical Archaeologist* 31: 1-32. Herzog, Ze'ev, Miriam Aharoni, Anson Rainey and Shmuel Moshkovitz. 1984. "The Israelite Fortress at Arad." *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 254: 1-34. Ussishkin, David. 1988. "The Date of the Judaeon Shrine at Arad." *Israel Exploration Journal* 38 (3): 142-57. See also: Arie, E., Rosen, B., and D. Namdar. 2020. "Cannabis and Frankincense at the Judahite Shrine of Arad." *Tel Aviv*: 47:5-28.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.imj.org.il/en/collections/369406>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1962-1967

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Arad Excavations conducted by the Archaeology Department of the Hebrew University, the Department of Antiquities of the Ministry of Education and Culture, and the Israel Exploration Society

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Other [specify]: Quarrying

Notes: The strata which the temple existed on were built upon a natural hill. However, a manmade cliff with a drop of 10m was found behind the dwellings on the western side of the fortress, the result of stone quarrying by the builders of the first Iron Age settlement (Herzog 2002: 16). Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." Tel Aviv 29 (1): 3-109.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: Though the temple itself is located in the corner of the fortress— that is, not centrally— its size takes up approximately one sixth of the total space within the fortress. Given the limited space within the fortress walls, its prominent size suggests the temple was significant to the people using it.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: Changes in the layouts of buildings from the 10th to 9th centuries indicate a shift from rural settlements to a more "centralised kingdom" (Herzog 2002: 95). Despite this, population numbers in the area did not increase once administrative centres and fortresses were built, likely due to worsening climate conditions that did not allow for permanent agriculture and settlement outside of a state-supplied fortification. Nonetheless, the temple at Arad and the Arad fortress itself can be considered to be in a more urbanized setting, but it should be noted that even in their own time this area was not very densely populated. Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." Tel Aviv 29 (1): 3-109. See especially section 9.5, pages 94-96.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The temple is an integral part of the fortress at Arad, taking up approximately one sixth of its interior space.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Sacrificial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The community which initially built the temple must have intended for it to last a long time, and the temple would have ideally remained in use. Later on however, the temple was ritually dismantled. Some scholars argue that this was to protect the temple from desecration by enemies, but Herzog argues against this, highlighting the fact that the temple was never rebuilt after its destruction (Herzog 2010: 181-183). Herzog, Ze'ev. 2010. "Perspectives on Southern Israel's Cult Centralization: Arad and Beer-Sheba." In *One God – One Cult – One Nation: Archaeological and Biblical Perspectives*, edited by R. G. Kratz and H. Spieckermann, 169–99. Berlin & New York: Walter de Gruyter.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The temple underwent some modifications from stratum X to stratum IX.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Buried

↳ With ritually deposited medium/material:

This might consist of pure sand, or a medium that has been consecrated.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

Notes: Scholars on the initial excavating team interpreted the destruction of the temple as evidence of cultic reform under the biblical king Hezekiah. Herzog argues that, while the archaeological record on its own does not provide proof of this, it appears the deliberate destruction of the temple reflects some sort of a religious revolution (Herzog 2010: 177). Since the fortress (and so the temple along with it) was supplied by the Kingdom of Judah, the cessation of use of the temple might also be tied into politics. Herzog, Ze'ev. 2010. "Perspectives on Southern Israel's Cult Centralization: Arad and Beer-Sheba." In *One God – One Cult – One Nation: Archaeological and Biblical Perspectives*, edited by R. G. Kratz and H. Spieckermann, 169–99. Berlin & New

York: Walter de Gruyter.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Yahweh

Notes: Though the temple has not preserved anything to explicitly identify itself with him, it was almost undoubtedly a temple of Yahweh given its being situated in a Judean fortress, and the kingdom's official association with the cult of Yahweh (Herzog: 2002, 68). Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." *Tel Aviv* 29 (1): 3-109.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Zevit suggests that in the stratum XI temple, there is a strong likelihood two deities were worshipped due to the pattern of "twoness" (ex. the two incense altars found in the temple), which he observes in other temples as well (Zevit 2001: 168). The second deity could perhaps be a consort to Yahweh. Zevit, Ziony. 2001. *The Religions of Ancient Israel: A Synthesis of Parallaxic Approaches*. New York: Continuum.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Field doesn't know

Notes: The fortress itself was built and supplied by the Kingdom of Judah, and so presumably the temple within it was also built by the Kingdom of Judah. Beyond this however, we do not know who

exactly called for its construction.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Kingdom of Judah put significant economic resources into the establishment of its fortification systems, including the fortress at Arad (Herzog 2002: 95). It seems likely that the temple might have also been supplied by the Kingdom, since the temple existed in the fortress "when desired," (Herzog 2002: 84) and was intentionally put out of operation, perhaps suggesting an external sponsor making decisions about its use. This is still speculation though, and we do not know definitively if the temple had an external sponsor. Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." *Tel Aviv* 29 (1): 3-109.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: While there is no explicit discussion of wood in the publications, we can assume wood was used in construction. Remnants of wooden beams were encountered elsewhere in the

fortress (Herzog 2002: 26, 76), along with impressions in the plaster and spacing in the structures (Herzog 2002: 40), which suggest there were once wooden structures present. Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." Tel Aviv 29 (1): 3-109.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: A carbonized wooden beam found in Locus 920 of the Stratum XI fortress was identified as *Pistacia atlantica*, a local species of tree (Herzog 2002: 26). Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." Tel Aviv 29 (1): 3-109.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The stones used to build the structure might have been taken from the very hill it was built upon; a manmade cliff dropping 10m was found behind the dwellings on the western side of the fortress. This cliff was likely the result of stone quarrying by the builders in the first Iron Age settlement (Herzog 2002: 16). Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." Tel Aviv 29 (1): 3-109.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Brick

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: An incense burner (a stand with bowl decorated with floral leaves) was found in the small room by the altar (Herzog 2002: 53).

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Two open bowls found at the foot of the altar were inscribed with the Hebrew letters qoph and kaph. This was interpreted as an abbreviation for qodesh kohanim, "set apart for the priests" (Herzog 2002: 56)

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: In the tradition of the Hebrew Bible, there are certain restricted areas within the temple, and rules that govern who can enter certain sacred spaces. The temple at Tel Arad seems to

mimic this structure, so it appears that objects such as the stone stela in the debir would be restricted from view.

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Field doesn't know

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While we can more reasonably assume objects like the stela in the debir would have been hidden, we do not know the extent to which other objects, such as the bowls, would have been hidden or accessible to the public.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Objects

Notes: Since it was intentionally dismantled, the temple lacked much decoration. Nonetheless, a variety of objects found in the temple structure and courtyard are worth mentioning: a stone stela with remnants of red paint, two incense altars with traces of organic material, two open bowls with inscribed Hebrew letters, and a small bronze figurine of a crouching lion. The temple's altar has imprints in its plaster that suggests there was once a metal basin there used for sacrifices (Herzog 2002: 62). Since the metal was valuable, it would have been removed prior to dismantling the temple, but it is worth noting here.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: A stela found in the debir did have remnants of red paint on it. Herzog notes that it lacked iconic features, indicating the temple might have conformed to biblical prohibitions against icons (Herzog 2002: 63-64). Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." *Tel Aviv* 29 (1): 3-109.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: There is no direct evidence linking Yahweh to the temple of Arad (inscriptions), though based on the religious practices of Judah, and the naming practices of the site in subsequent generations, it is overwhelmingly likely that Yahweh was the deity of focus (perhaps with a consort).

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Yahweh appears to have originally held the role of a "storm deity" and "divine warrior" within the southern Levantine pantheon. See discussion in: Toorn, Karel van der. 1999.

"Yahweh." In *Dictionary of Deities and Demons in the Bible*, edited by Karel van der Toorn, Bob Becking, and Pieter W. van der Horst, 2nd- Revised ed., 910-19. Leiden: Brill.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– I don't know

Notes: Yahweh is presented as the dynastic god (as well as a popular "local" god). See discussion in: Sanders, Seth. 2015. "When the Personal Became Political: An Onomastic Perspective on the Rise of Yahwism." *Hebrew Bible and Ancient Israel* 4: 78-105.

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ostensibly, yes, in abstract ways (based on regional comparisons).

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A standing stone was excavated within the most sacred part of the temple (debir; holy of holies). It is possible that these are abstract representations of a deity.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The gods would certainly be honored and sacrificed to. The degree to which there was "communication" may be debated. The sacrifices were likely intended toward appeasement and/or supplication for the gods.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Sheep and goat are the most common form of sacrificed animal.

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As the site was intentionally decommissioned, much of the material culture from within was likely removed. Thus, while there were likely material offerings, beyond a few scattered remains, the floors of the temple were largely devoid of objects. See discussion in: Herzog, Ze'ev. 2010.

“Perspectives on Southern Israel’s Cult Centralization: Arad and Beer-Sheba.” In *One God – One Cult – One Nation: Archaeological and Biblical Perspectives*, edited by R. G. Kratz and H. Spieckermann, 169–99. Berlin & New York: Walter de Gruyter.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably, yes.

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The site lacks a final report that contextualizes the provenience of the material culture. It is certainly possible that group commensality took place at Temple, for which the southern Levant has good precedent. See for example, Greer's (2013) work at Tel Dan. Greer, Jonathan. 2013. Dinner at Dan: Biblical and Archaeological Evidence for Sacred Feasts at Iron Age II Tel Dan and Their Significance. *Culture and History of the Ancient Near East* 66. Leiden: Brill.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably yes, though there is no direct evidence of such.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is probable that divination was practiced, though direct evidence is lacking.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unknown

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Hebrew Bible, particularly the Deuteronomist, preserves strict guidelines for appropriate religious practice. Ironically, according to the Deuteronomist, the very Temple at Arad itself would be a breach of ideal behavior. Here, chronology is a factor as the Temple of Arad was decommissioned in the late 8th century BCE, roughly contemporaneous with the early period of religious reform, to the extent it was present in the late 8th century BCE (2 Kings 18), prior to more intensified activity in the late 7th century BCE (2 Kings 22-23). However, the apparent care with which the temple was decommissioned would appear to indicate it was not the recipient of any strict enforcement of religious orthopraxy. See discussion in: Herzog, Ze'ev. 2010. "Perspectives on Southern Israel's Cult Centralization: Arad and Beer-Sheba." In *One God – One Cult – One Nation: Archaeological and Biblical Perspectives*, edited by R. G. Kratz and H. Spieckermann, 169–99. Berlin & New York: Walter de Gruyter. Fried, Lisbeth S. 2002. "The High Places (Bāmôt) and the Reforms of Hezekiah and Josiah: An Archaeological Investigation." *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 122 (3): 437–65.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Several incense altars were excavated in the Temple. Subsequent residue analysis has revealed evidence of frankincense and cannabis (Arie et al. 2020) among other possible intoxicants. Likewise, alcohol in the form of wine, is a prominent feature of the region. Arie, E., Rosen, B., and D. Namdar. 2020. "Cannabis and Frankincense at the Judahite Shrine of Arad." *Tel Aviv*: 47:5-28.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Presumably yes, religious specialists were in charge of the functioning of the temple.

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Technically unknown for this particular context, though on the basis of parallels from Jerusalem in Judah, and the traditions of the Hebrew Bible, it is more than likely that the persons in charge of the Arad Temple were male.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We may presume that the majority of specialists at the temple, as well as ritual participants came from the Kingdom of Judah, though it is likely best not to refer to this as an ethnicity. The fortifications of the site suggest that the Temple was not accessible to all, but primarily those associated or friendly to the Judahite administration.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: From the Hebrew Bible there is evidence of "Priestly classes" of people (e.g., Aaronides, Zadokites, Levites), though it is unclear to what extent these traditions may be applied to contexts such as the Temple at Arad that have no mention within the biblical text.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no direct data for hierarchies from Arad, though from comparisons to the Hebrew Bible and Jerusalem it is possible that there would have been hierarchies and/or that religious activity at Arad was nested within a broader regional religious system.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: There are several rooms adjacent the ritual spaces of the temple that could in theory have been used to housed religious specialist. However, based on the material culture found within, comparison to similar contexts, and the interpretation of the excavators, these rooms were used as storage, and for the more economic aspects of temple life (Herzog 2002: 52-62). The religious specialists at Arad most likely lived within the fort, in the domestic spaces beyond the temple yet within the walls of the fort. Herzog, Ze'ev. 2002. "The Fortress Mound at Tel Arad: An Interim Report." *Tel Aviv* 29 (1): 3-109.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: There was no formal bureaucracy associated with the temple, though the site of Arad was linked to the Judahite military administration. Thus, while not associated with the temple, there is evidence for bureaucracy at the fort. This bureaucracy is evident in a series of ostraca largely from the subsequent centuries that are published in: Aharoni, Yohanan. 1981. *Arad Inscriptions*. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: There was no writing stored in the temple, though a series of ostraca were excavated at Tel Arad in the period subsequent the temple's intentional dismantlement. These ostraca are published in: Aharoni, Yohanan. 1981. *Arad Inscriptions*. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No